

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR PREPARING FUTURE EDUCATORS TO FORM THE FOUNDATIONS OF HEALTH PRESERVATION AND LIFE SAFETY IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article substantiates the pedagogical conditions for preparing future educators to form the foundations of health preservation and life safety in preschool children. It emphasizes the growing importance of training preschool teachers who can develop children's value-based attitudes toward health, safe behavior, and personal well-being. The study interprets professional readiness as an integrated structure consisting of motivational-value-based, cognitive, and activity-based components. It also identifies cognitive, motivational, creative, personality-oriented, and activity-oriented criteria for assessing students' readiness. The proposed pedagogical conditions include the formation of stable motivation for health-preserving activity, systematic acquisition of theoretical knowledge, interdisciplinary integration, modeling of professional activity, practice-oriented tasks, and educational project development. The results of experimental work showed positive dynamics in the experimental group, especially in motivational and activity-based criteria. The findings confirm the effectiveness of the proposed pedagogical conditions for improving future educators' professional readiness.*

Keywords: *health preservation, life safety, preparation of educators, pedagogical conditions, professional readiness, preschool education.*

Introduction

The modern system of preschool education is oriented toward forming in children the foundations of a healthy lifestyle and safe behavior, which is determined both by social demand and by the strategic directions of education development in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Under these conditions, the role of the teacher as a key subject of the educational process increases, ensuring not only the transmission of knowledge but also the formation in children of a value-based attitude toward their own health and safety. Consequently, the problem of high-quality training of pedagogical personnel capable of implementing health-preserving activity on a scientifically grounded and methodologically verified basis acquires special significance [4].

In scientific and pedagogical research, the professional readiness of future educators is considered a complex integrative formation that includes a set of personal, cognitive, and activity-based characteristics ensuring success in professional activity. Within the framework of this study, professional readiness is interpreted as the unity of three interrelated components: motivational-value-based, cognitive, and activity-based, which corresponds to modern understandings of the competence-based approach in education.

The motivational-value-based component reflects the formation of the professional orientation of the future teacher's personality, their attitude toward the problems of health preservation and life safety, as well as the level of awareness of the social significance of this

activity. This component is system-forming, since it is value orientations that determine the nature of professional behavior and the degree of the student's involvement in the educational process.

The cognitive component includes a system of theoretical knowledge in the field of health preservation, developmental psychology, the basics of life safety, as well as methods for forming them in preschool children. It is important to note that this component is not reduced to the simple accumulation of knowledge, but presupposes their meaningful assimilation, structuring, and the ability to transfer them to new pedagogical situations [6].

The activity-based component characterizes the level of formation of practical abilities and skills for organizing an educational process aimed at forming preschool children's initial ideas about health and safety. It is manifested in the teacher's ability to design educational situations, apply modern pedagogical technologies, and adapt teaching methods while taking into account the individual characteristics of children [3].

It should be emphasized that the presented structure of professional readiness correlates with modern ideas about the professional competence of a teacher, in which the cognitive, operational, and value-motivational aspects of activity are integrated.

Materials and Methods

For an objective assessment of the level of formation of the indicated components, the following criteria were identified: cognitive, motivational, creative, personality-oriented, and activity-oriented. Such an expansion of the criteria apparatus is methodologically justified, since the components reflect the structure of formation, while the criteria reflect the result and degree of its manifestation. Each criterion included a system of indicators that make it possible to diagnose both the level of knowledge and the nature of its application in professional activity [5].

In particular, the cognitive criterion was assessed according to the level of assimilation of theoretical knowledge and the ability to interpret it analytically; the motivational criterion was assessed according to the expression of professional interest and a value-based attitude toward health-preserving activity; the activity-based criterion was assessed according to the ability to apply knowledge in practical situations; the creative criterion was assessed according to the level of formation of the ability to solve pedagogical tasks in variable and non-standard ways; and the personality-oriented criterion was assessed according to the degree to which the individual characteristics of the child were taken into account in the educational process [1].

In the course of the study, pedagogical conditions ensuring the effectiveness of preparing future educators were substantiated. At the same time, it is fundamentally important to emphasize that these conditions are considered not in isolation, but as an interconnected system ensuring the holistic formation of professional readiness.

The first pedagogical condition is connected with the formation of students' stable motivation for health-preserving activity. Its implementation is ensured through the use of problem-based learning, analysis of pedagogical situations, and reflective tasks aimed at understanding personal experience. This condition contributes to the transition from external motivation to an internal professional position [2].

The second condition presupposes the systematic acquisition of theoretical knowledge based on the use of structured educational materials, interdisciplinary integration, and the scientific validity of the content. This ensures the formation of a holistic picture of professional activity and prevents the fragmentation of knowledge.

The third condition is aimed at developing practical skills through modeling professional activity, completing practice-oriented tasks, and developing educational projects. The use of the

situational approach becomes especially significant here, as it makes it possible to bring the educational process closer to the real conditions of professional activity [7].

The implementation of the indicated pedagogical conditions was carried out in stages within the framework of a pedagogical experiment. At the ascertaining stage, the initial level of formation of students' professional readiness was determined, which made it possible to identify existing deficits. At the formative stage, the targeted implementation of pedagogical conditions ensuring the development of all components of readiness was carried out. The control stage was aimed at repeated diagnostics and comparative analysis of the results.

To ensure the reliability of the research results, a set of methods was used, including questionnaires, testing, observation, and analysis of students' activity products. Data processing was carried out using mathematical and statistical methods, which made it possible to ensure the objectivity and scientific validity of the results obtained [4].

Results

The results of the experiment indicate the presence of positive dynamics in the experimental group according to all the identified criteria. It was established that the proportion of students with a high level of professional readiness increased significantly, whereas the number of students with a low level decreased. On average, the increase in indicators amounted to approximately 12% compared with the control group, which confirms the effectiveness of the implemented system of pedagogical conditions.

Particularly pronounced changes were observed according to the activity-based and motivational criteria, which indicates the formation of a stable professional position and an increase in the level of students' practical readiness. This result is of fundamental importance, since these components determine the teacher's ability to engage in real professional activity [2].

Discussion

The obtained results show that the proposed pedagogical conditions had a positive influence on the professional readiness of future educators. The most significant changes in the activity-based and motivational criteria indicate that students not only acquired theoretical knowledge but also developed a more stable professional position and practical readiness for health-preserving educational activity. This demonstrates that the integration of problem-based learning, analysis of pedagogical situations, reflective tasks, interdisciplinary knowledge, and practice-oriented projects can improve the preparation of future educators for working with preschool children. Therefore, the findings confirm the importance of organizing professional training as a systematic process that combines motivation, knowledge, and practical activity.

Conclusion

Thus, the conducted study allows us to conclude that the effectiveness of preparing future educators to form the foundations of health preservation and life safety in preschool children is determined by the systematic implementation of a complex of pedagogical conditions that ensure the integration of the motivational, cognitive, and activity-based components of professional readiness. The results obtained may be used in the system of higher pedagogical education, as well as in the practice of professional development for pedagogical personnel.

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